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INDEPENDENCE OF JUDGES IS ONE OF THE GUARANTEES OF ACQUITTAL VERDICT

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The state in its activity is based on the principles of social justice and legality, and the activity of the courts also belongs to these principles. In the judicial sphere, the principle of legality is expressed in its own form, i.e.: in the administration of justice, this principle is combined with the principle of independence of judges, and they act based on the requirements of the applicable law, their legal consciousness and inner confidence in making judgments.

In order to hold the position of a judge, a person must be of a certain age, have a higher legal education, have sufficient life and professional experience, and most importantly, have good conscience ¹.

The essence of the principle of independence of judges is to strive to ensure the conditions that provide a real opportunity for the court to make responsible decisions without outside interference, without any pressure or other influence, strictly following the requirements of the law ².

reflected in the relations of the court with other participants in the criminal proceedings, with other institutions, organizations, officials and citizens . In Chapter 8, Article 67 of the Law "On Courts", the independence of judges is ensured by:

- a) electing, appointing and dismissing them as judges in the manner prescribed by law;
- b) their inviolability ;
- c) fair trial done increasing strictly food _
- g) decision release during judges confidentiality of advice and him disclosed to do demand of reaching ban ;
- d) to court disrespect or certain things solution to do interference , judges inviolability violation for responsibility ;

¹ Abdumajidov G'.A. and others _ Judiciary in Uzbekistan : reforms era .- T.: Adolat , 2002. -B.58.

² Paleev M.S., Pashin S.A., Savitsky V. M. Law on the status of judges in the Russian Federation. Scientific and practical commentary. /Pod ed. V.M. Savitskogo.- M.: BEK, 1994.-B.79.

e) to the judge state at the expense of his high status worthy material and social supply to give

Judges independence from the principle come out , they are Criminal-procedural and crime to the legislation Based on the crime their work solution they do Theirs to the activity each how intervention the law according to to responsibility take will come This judges of independence from guarantees is one and it is JK 's " Adil to trial against It is confirmed in Article 236 of the " Crimes " chapter .

The law is in court all to the circumstances their own internal beliefs according to price to give necessity shown . Evidence in assessment internal trust rely on problem from before scientists between many sharp to discussions reason being came _ Process worker of scientists some of them internal trust evaluation method , method or principle ³, some of them evaluation criterion or his the result⁴ again others while this of properties summary⁵ in the style of definition those who gave Internal of trust nature sometimes epistemological or logical , sometimes spiritual in a sense interpretation will be done . This to the matter interest random not _ Because procedural of activity success a lot in terms of internal trust based on the evidence evaluation the issue right solution to be done depend _ Of this for first of all internal trust concept analysis reach it is necessary In the law in the eye caught internal trust the following in content interpretation to be done to the goal suitable : a) to someone (including to himself also) is known one to look , to do absorb process ; b) this of the process result , that is sure one to the idea , to the thought to arrive c) of a person own knowledge , decisions and to his actions has been relationship , that is confidence , to be sure status _

So so , internal trust check process and his from the result consists of of the law internal trust about demand work take going to the individual given authority as too to understand can _ This authority through his the evidence evaluation in the field privileges strengthen and evaluate directly his the right and obligation the fact that again note once _ will be done . This is the court task another to the individual to upload or another persons by given grades judgment in release to apply right not _

³ See : Kaz Ts.M. Evidence and criminal proceedings. -Saratov: 1960. -B. 23-25; Trusov A.I. Basic theory of judicial evidence. -M.: 1960. -B. 48-51 and others _

⁴Arsenev V.D. Voprosy obshchey teorii sudebnykh dokazatelstv. -M.: 1964. -B. 92; Strogovich M.S. The course of the ugolovno process. T. 1. -M.: Nauka, 1968. -B. 288-289.

⁵The course of the ugolovno process. Obshchaya chast. /Pod ed. A.D. Boykova and I.I. Karpetsa -M : 1989. -B. 551.

Court evidence in assessment free and independent respectively activity walks _ This valid of legislation one row in the norms reinforced . Internal trust each how external coercion , influence an exception is enough Tan get must be " from above " illegal and not justified instructions to give cases available ⁶, but crime work in conducting it or this conditions to determine for many investigators , prosecutors and courts procedural actions done increases , process participants with in communication will be , directly their morals , behavior observes , to questions given the answers compares , collected to the evidence based on the law based on , full , har bilaterally and impartiality with and own internal trust relied on without them evaluates . That's why for of the court procedural independence - court actions in transfer the law priority of provision mandatory from the conditions is one⁷

H of the verdict its legitimacy _ material and procedural right norms strictly is compatibility . Judgment material right norms compatibility when you say then in JK norms substances use , crime qualification , type of punishment and size , material damage charge and another of issues right solution done is understood . This in case not only crime in the law , but also civil , labor and another material right in the fields to work concerned of norms right used attention is taken.

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⁶Akhmedov T.E., Mukhammadaliev D.S. Characteristic of nekotorykh factors, sposobstvuyushchikh protivodeystviyu rassledovaniya. // Law , Pravo , Law . -1998. - No. 2. -B.43.

⁷Egorov K. Osobennosti otsenki dokazatelstv pri sedebnom control. // Judge Rossiisky. -2000. - No. 4. - B. 25-27.

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